

When the West is Checkmated

For several years now, people and social media have been discussing the issue of *Aghazadehs* (a term referring to the privileged children of high-ranking officials in Iran). Nearly all children of officials from the Islamic Republic are living in Western countries in complete comfort and without worries. Meanwhile, their fathers continue to curse and chant slogans against the West. Yet, the children of these vocal critics reside in the very same so-called “cursed” countries.

There is no doubt that the officials of the Islamic Republic are hypocritical and two-faced, but the story of their children in the West is not merely about pleasure-seeking or enjoying vast, unearned wealth. In reality, these children act as trusted infiltrators of the Islamic Republic, tasked with safeguarding the regime’s interests in the West. By studying abroad and engaging in various businesses, they subtly infiltrate different spheres and eliminate individuals deemed threats to the regime—sometimes through bribery or other means—without making noise.

What many fail to understand is that a significant number of these *Aghazadehs* now hold citizenship in Western countries. With their deep understanding of the West, they operate freely within the frameworks of Western liberties, including freedom of speech. They have skillfully identified the West’s weak points and are exploiting them like termites.

With their wealth, they have even entered influential Western families, quietly advancing the Islamic Republic’s agenda. These *Aghazadehs*, as Ayatollah Khamenei himself admitted, are now fully grown men and women, and are not easily identifiable. They are regular attendees of Western social gatherings, parties, and elite circles, wearing suits and ties, while their women often appear completely unveiled and without hijab.

Anyone familiar with Iran’s intelligence apparatus knows that the regime has provided all these individuals with religious decrees and permissions to do whatever is necessary to preserve the system.

Therefore, it shouldn't surprise anyone when the daughter of a high-ranking official appears without a hijab or when the son of another official is seen drunk and carousing.

This is why, when one of these *Aghazadehs* is exposed, the Islamic regime passes over the news in meaningful silence. This silence reflects the special tasks these individuals are entrusted with. The regime seeks to secure its survival by infiltrating any place it can abroad. It can be confidently said that in any gathering of twenty Iranians, at least one is an informant. This is why every opposition plan ends up on the desks of the regime's intelligence services even before being fully examined.

I don't wish to exaggerate, but we must recognize that naivety breeds failure. Beyond the global political backroom deals, the role of the officials' children demands special attention. A Western journalist earns approximately about two to three thousand euros a month. Such a person can easily be swayed with a ten-thousand-euro gift. This isn't to say everyone can be bought, but in most situations, money buys influence.

Understanding these matters and the Islamic Republic's dirty games is of critical importance. What has checkmated the West is the fact that many of these officials' children are now Western citizens, with some even marrying into prominent families in these countries. John Kerry's son-in-law is an obvious example. Undoubtedly, John Kerry is a caring grandfather who would do anything for his grandchildren. He would even sacrifice himself to ensure his daughter and grandchildren are not distressed. This is where the Islamic Republic's cunning lies. Therefore, the influence of officials' children shouldn't be dismissed as mere indulgence in pleasure and luxury.

When China sends students to the United States, it does so with two primary goals: (1) espionage and (2) stealing advanced technologies. The Islamic Republic, however, aims primarily at dominating intelligence networks and infiltrating various academic, journalistic, and artistic circles to, as they claim, "export the revolution."

While part of this game is indeed to justify the officials' spending on their children, a significant portion is genuinely dedicated to preserving the regime. The Islamic

Republic's plan involves infiltrating every university, every major newspaper, and every artistic and cultural space.

The Islamic Republic has managed to extend its influence even into Western casinos, brothels, and gatherings that appear, on the surface, to be entirely at odds with Islamic principles. While Western intelligence agencies are not entirely oblivious and actively monitor many of these activities, the Islamic Republic has mastered a level of subtlety in its interactions with the West that makes addressing these issues exceedingly difficult. This is partly because the regime has succeeded in infiltrating not just public institutions but also the private lives of many Western officials.

The Western world operates based on its own interests, and the Islamic Republic, fully aware of this dynamic, demonstrates a willingness to sacrifice virtually anything—including moral and social values—to maintain its grip on power. For the preservation of authority, the clerical establishment has shown no hesitation in justifying morally questionable actions, often citing historical Islamic narratives, hadiths, or even fabricating evidence to validate their conduct.

Anyone who assumes that the clerical leadership of Iran possesses a sense of national honor or moral red lines is gravely mistaken. The same establishment that once labeled Iraqi Shiites as “Ba’athist” and “filthy,” advocating for their persecution and death, on another day, the same “Shia Ba’athist” engages in temporary marriages (*sigheh*) with an Iranian women in religious cities like Mashhad, even gets celebrated by the same who labeled him to begin with.

What the West fails to comprehend is that while the immediate victims of the Islamic Republic's policies are the people of Iran, in the long run, Western societies themselves will bear the brunt of these strategies. The children of Iranian officials have already integrated into Western communities, becoming part of the free and open society that the West prides itself on, and they wield significant influence from within.

The only viable solution to address this growing issue lies in a rigorous, uncompromising approach—one akin to the measures taken against ISIS networks.

Terrorism is not confined to acts of physical violence or suicide bombings; it can also manifest in more insidious forms, such as cultural, ethical, and social subversion. Soft terrorism operates subtly, stripping away legitimate freedoms and corroding societal values over time. While hard terrorism claims lives in an instant, soft terrorism kills slowly and silently, as seen in places like North Korea, Cuba, or Iran.

Organizations like the National Iranian American Council (*NIAC*) represent only the visible tip of a much larger iceberg—one that consists of an extensive and well-coordinated network of influence operations orchestrated by the Islamic Republic.

Even now, significant time has been lost. If decisive action is not taken to address the issue of Iranian officials' children and their deep integration into Western societies, the world may soon face a threat even more dangerous than the overt brutality of hard terrorism.